

Acknowledgement to reviewers

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) wishes to thank all the reviewers for their intellectual contributions by timely reviewing manuscripts, and supporting the journal's vision of "*Enriching Beautiful Minds towards Intelligent Minds*".

From the desk of the Editor-in-Chief, the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) would like to thank all the reviewers who made it possible to publish this volume, Volume 10, Issue 1, May 2026.

We will not publish the reviewers' names to protect their confidentiality and maintain academic integrity.

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TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

